

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2025 Authors

**A Critique of Immaunel Kant's
Ontological Argument on the Existence of
God and Human Fanatical Tendencies**

Kelvin OBINECHE

*Department of Religious Studies, Faculty of Arts,
National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja*
ahannakelvin@gmail.com, +2348030635512

Abstract

This paper is a critique of Immanuel Kant ontological argument on the existence of God and human fanatical tendencies. Fanatics' thinking is excessively rigid. The belief in its immediate and extraordinary communion with a higher nature. Immanuel Kant lived within the medieval philosophical era, an era marked with lots of ontological argument about the existence of God. The argument appropriated by fanatics' lies within their core theological belief and doctrine. The mission within is to advance the values of their supreme communion with God which provides justification for its intransigent certainty' using the tools of deductive and inductive reasoning, the learner seeks to comprehend and critique the idea of the existence of God postulated by Immanuel Kant. And it impacts fanatical ideologies. Thus, using the critical analytical method of data collection, the paper concludes that to establish logical thesis and synthesis, it requires a critique of Immanuel Kant ontological argument that existence of God within the confines of deductive and inductive reasoning.

Keywords: God's Existence, Ontological Argument, Fanaticism, Logical Fallacies

Introduction

The age of enlightenment in the late 17th through the 18th century ushered in numerous arguments across different fields of human endeavours, the believe of God existence and moral will as against illogical postulations of religious ideology. Chiefly in Europe, intellectuals began to question many fields of knowledge that have been held over previous centuries. Religion was a major field that was lampooned as many philosophical ideologies rose and gave room for 'Reason' other than 'Faith'. "Atheism in this era rose to high recognition, that the idea of the existence of a God was a mere human construct to help deal with how to handle the vicissitudes of life and not a reality, since the existence of such a being can neither be proven empirically or scientifically" (Kant, 1889:223). Many theists have given arguments for the existence of God from one philosophical era to another, Thomas Aquinas, St. Anselm of Canterbury and other Christian apologetic philosophers in defence of theism and tried to give justification for their 'Faith' and to prove the existence of God.

The medieval period and the dark age also experience wars murders and other inhumane activities that uses religion to justify their action, this gave room and momentum to atheism and religious skepticism there assertions remain in their assumptions that God allow such heinous unpardonable human crimes suggesting that a benevolent God cannot 'BE' and allows such inhuman act if so, he is no all loving God as acclaim by his followers, thus the rejection of the existence of God. Logically, these medieval thoughts led to the rejection of the idea of the existence of God.

Adherent of both Islam and Christianity laid claim to classical theism. Bigotry gave rise to fanaticism which is an "Unwillingness to recognize and respect difference in opinion or belief" (Hudson, 1998:10). Immanuel Kant was a German and one of the early modern enlightenment thinkers. His major arguments on fanaticism and logic were centred on his 17th century famous quotes: "that political legitimacy, morality and knowledge are not to be grounded on divine right, religiosity or revealed doctrine but rather on reasons, logic and rational knowledge of human nature alone" (Pluhar, 1790:174).

Kant assert us that; fanaticism believe itself to feel an immediate and extraordinary communion with the Supreme Being which provides its antecedence toward a seemingly justifiable intransigent certainty; the major difference between such views as upheld by fanatical ideology is the fact that God cannot be proved in relation to a personal on sided subjective view of God that is devoid of logical synthesis. His ontological argument for and existence of God states that it is impossible to conceive God as not existing because the very concept implies that he exists. Thus, using the critical analytic method of data collection and special study of other books and articles written by other authors, this paper concludes that Immanuel Kant assertion on fanatic's belief is centred on the illegitimacy of classical theism.

The Concept of God on Religious Tradition

The existence of a being that has certain attributes to him/them of which humans owe their existence to becomes necessary when one subscribes to a certain religious tradition. Since religion is as old as man, the human being has seen the need to hold the belief in the existence of a supreme being maybe because of certain inherent deficiencies he has over nature and the vicissitudes of life as some classical theories of religion suggest. While those who belief in the existence of God/gods are theist, those who do not belief in the existence of God are atheist.

God is often conceived as the greatest entity in existence. God is often believed to be the cause of all things and so is seen as the creator, sustainer, and ruler of the universe. God is often thought of as incorporeal and independent of the material creation, while pantheism holds that God is the universe itself. God is sometimes seen as omnibenevolent. The dominant idea of God in western civilization, then, is the idea of a supremely good being, creator of but separate from and independent of the world, all-powerful (omnipotent), all-knowing (omniscient), eternal, and self-existent. The God of monotheism is the one real god that is believed to exist, or, in any case, that is acknowledged as such. God's essence and character are believed to be unique and fundamentally different from all other beings that can be considered comparable e.g., the gods of other religions.

According to Luman, "Christianity, perhaps more than any other religion, has a well-developed concept of God. The attributes ascribed to God derive partly from revelation and partly from philosophical reflection of the nature

of the greatest imaginable being worthy of worship” (Louden 1798: 227-429). For God to be the greatest imaginable being worthy of worship he must be a being who maximizes all possible qualities like power, knowledge and goodness. He must also exist eternally and therefore cannot have any equals. The nature of God is often explained in the following way:

1. He is an Omnipresent Spirit. He knows what is happening everywhere without being dependent for that knowledge on anything or anyone else. He is a spirit because he could not have to depend on physical organs like eyes and nerves to convey knowledge that he did not already have. Also having a body would limit him to a particular time and space.
2. He is the Creator of all things, responsible for the past, present and future existence of material objects and the laws that govern them.
3. He is Omnipotent, that can do everything that is logically possible to know.
4. He is Omniscient, that is, knowing at any time, what is possible to know.
5. He is Eternal by nature rather than choice. He cannot choose to cease to exist.
6. He is Perfect, that is God performs any morally right action but does not perform any morally bad action.

It is a simpler concept of God than that of polytheism because it does not need to be explained in terms of anything else. The monotheistic God has qualities that essentially belong together and provides a total personal explanation for everything else that exists.

Argument for and against the Existence of God

Critique of Speculative Theology

Kant criticizes all the traditional arguments for the existence into three kinds, namely:

- i. ***The ontological argument***, he says, is based on the concept of God as the ensrealissimum, i.e., the most real being. According to this argument, God is the absolutely perfect and necessary being, the total of all perfections and the subject of all possible predicates. Since existence is perfection and a predicate, God, the subject of all predicates and the total of all perfections must have existence. “It is therefore impossible to conceive God as not existing because the very

concept of God implies that he exists. In fact, it would, according to this argument, be self-contradictory to say that God does not exist” (Infield, 1963:36).

Kant does not dismiss this argument by saying that existence is not perfection nor is it a predicate. To add the idea of existence to any being is not to add anything to the concept of that being, for the concept of existence is inseparably part of the concept of any being. To take away the concept of existence from the concept of any being is to take away the concept of the being with all its predicates. It is therefore not self-contradictory, says Kant, to deny the existence of God because to deny the existence of God does not mean to affirm God as a being and deny his existence, but rather it means to deny the whole idea of God as a being - and not simply his existence while retaining his idea as a being.

To suppress the existence of a triangle and angles is perfectly admissible. And so, it is with the conception of a necessary being. Annihilate its existence in thought, and you annihilate the thing itself with all its predicates; how then can there be any room for contradiction.

This argument is therefore invalid, and Kant concludes by saying that:

“All the trouble and labor bestowed on the famous ontological or Cartesian proof of the existence of a supreme being from concepts alone is trouble and laborwasted. Man might as well expect to become richer in knowledge by the aid of mere ideas as a merchant to increase his wealth by adding some naught to his cash account ”(Auxier, 2023).

ii. *Cosmological Argument*

Kant expresses the cosmological argument as follows:

If anything exists, an infinitely necessary being must also exist.

Now, I at exist.

Therefore, an absolutely necessary being exists.

“The concept of causality is one of the *apriori* concepts (categories) of human understanding which cannot be validly and meaningfully applied beyond the sphere of sense experience. Moreover, the cosmological argument is really ‘an older argument in a new dress’ for it is also based on the concept of necessary being, a concept employed

in the ontological argument and already refuted in the argument. Besides, like ontological argument, the cosmological argument confuses the logical possibility of a thing being conceived with the fact of its existence. But the fact that I can conceive the logical possibility of a thing existing does not mean that it really exists” (Pasternack, 2014).

iii. Physico-Theological Argument

The Physico– theological argument is the argument from design. That the universe manifests order, harmony, wisdom and purposefulness. The universe must therefore be the product of an intelligent being who is responsible for the order, harmony and purposefulness observable in it. Kant’s taught this argument is inadequate to prove the existence of God, but it has best prove the existence of an architect or a design of the world but not a creator.

The existence of God can neither be proved nor disproved in Kant’s view. According to him, “it is just as impossible to disprove God’s existence as it is to prove his existence by any speculative argument” (Wood, 1999). Kant of course believes in God, but this is not because of any rational argument demonstrating his existence. He thinks that a better way to approach the question of God’s existence is by way of morality rather that by metaphysical arguments.

Immanuel Kant: Ontological Thesis on Fanaticism

Many seventeenth- and eighteenth-century philosophers argue that political legitimacy, morality, and knowledge be grounded on divine right, religiosity, or revealed doctrine, but rather on reason and rational knowledge of human nature alone. These philosophers are both inspired by scientific advances and attempting to limit the power of religion in response to centuries of religiously inspired political violence in Europe.

Hobbes, Spinoza, Locke, Shaftesbury, Hume, Voltaire, and Diderot, for example, criticize religious doctrines not only because (or when) such doctrines comprise unfounded claims to knowledge, but also because they inspire religious fanaticism, ensuing in sectarian violence, persecution, torture, and war. These thinkers by and large argue that fanaticism is the expression of irrational, emotional aspects of human psychology, exploited by some forms of religion: political ambitions of religious leaders, hopes and

fears of the population, overweening conceit, or a diseased melancholy. Thus, religious fanaticism or “enthusiasm” could, they argue, be curbed by reducing the political power of religious institutions, by rational polemics against the claims to superior knowledge and morality of religious leaders, by rational politics that could address people’s earthly hopes and fears, and by education, the inculcation of instrumental and/or moral rationality in the population at large.

Kant is recognizably a participant in this tradition. Kant too argues that politics ought to be governed by a rational principle of right and take the form of republican government; that freedom of religion (and the independence of political governance from religious institutions) ought to be instituted in such a state; that “morality derives from principles of pure practical reason; and that human beings may legitimately claim to know scientific laws concerning objects of sensible experience, but not to have knowledge of God or other spiritual, supersensible matters. And Kant too repeatedly and pejoratively characterizes various forms of belief in or behavior guided by religious (or other) conceptions of the supersensible as fanaticism” (Allison, 1990).

Kant’s talked about fanaticism in two forms:

- a. Theoretical fanaticism: Kant’s claim that human beings can attain knowledge of things in themselves or noumena.
- b. Practical fanaticism: are those that involve immoral action, including action that harms the fanatical agent himself, may be condemned as violations of the moral law. The claim that “God told me” Based on the revelation the individual receives from God.

Kant’s distinction between theoretical and practical reason generates an interesting, dual account of fanaticism, or of how human beings may stand in wrong relation to supersensible; he identifies both a theoretical fanaticism, a kind of cognitive error, and a practical fanaticism, a specifically practical error in our relation to the supersensible.

Critique of Immanuel Kant’s Thesis on Fanatism

Kant’s account of fanaticism critique was believed to be a scattered provocative remark and need to reconstruct his account of fanaticism; particularly practical fanaticism, as it is the most pressing, worrying form of fanaticism, both for enlightenment figures and for us. Let’s start by presenting Kants’ account of theoretical fanaticism, before turning to its

relation to practical reason and to his account of practical fanaticism. But first we need to clarify Kants terminology.

Let our concern be on Kants conception of “Schwärmerei” and will argue that this may be analyzed as comprising of two sorts of error: “theoretical fanaticism” and “practical fanaticism” (Guyer, 1993)¹. As these neologisms suggest, Kant’s conception of Schwärmerei does not map neatly into current English usage of “fanaticism” (which does not have a “theoretical” epistemic cast or subcategory). The Cambridge translations of Kants works tend to render Schwärmerei as “enthusiasm”. Thus, also bringing it into contact with eighteenth – century British discussions concerning problematic types of religious belief and action.

“There are good reasons for translating Schwämerei as "enthusiasm," for the usage of these two terms in the eighteenth century is roughly coincident, and considerably broader and less defined than the already somewhat fuzzy "fanaticism" in current English usage” (Korsgaard, 1996) “Enthusiasm” we may infare was sometimes associated with the word zeal, nationalism, and bigotry. In English language "fanaticism" was used to “characterize religious sectarianism, extremism, and violence” (Beiser, 1987) .

But it was also used to refer to a wider range of beliefs and behaviours, to “groups and individuals who claimed to have direct divine inspiration, who prophesied about future events, who claimed to perform miracles, whose activities involved physical manifestations such as convulsions," or who were characterized by “exaggerated religious spirituality" or endorsed an “emotional, personal, and...experiential type of religion" Thus “enthusiasm" need not refer to any sort of practical attitude, much less a tendency to violent action-as “fanaticism” connotes today but may refer more broadly to emotional excess or mistaken belief held on the grounds of question-able evidence. Specifically, such questionable evidence--as is suggested in the etymology of "enthusiasm" (Palmquist, 1993). Often comprises putative direct personal revelation or inspiration.

"Schwamerei" in Kant's usage tends to have this broader extension, for Kant often uses it to characterize epistemic failings, thereby, deemphasizing the political connotations of the term. (Here, as I shall discuss, Kant is not too

distant from Locke's account of enthusiasm in the *Essay Concerning Human Understanding*) Kant frequently uses this term to refer to those who make mistaken claims to knowledge superior to that of ordinary human beings, usually of super sensible reality. Like some British critics of enthusiasm, Kant often associates “Schwāmerei with mysticism, but also criticizes as Schwärmerei Platonists who claim to have immediate, intuitive knowledge of the Forms, Spinoza and Spinozists, and even Locke, for claiming to garner a priori concepts (including that of God) from empirical evidence, thereby "opening the gates" to Schwāmerei” (Yovel, 1980). Kant's most extensive discussion of Schwadmerei is in the early work, *Dreams of a Spirit Seer Elucidated by Dreams of Metaphysics*, his mocking engagement with Emmanuel Swedenborg's claims of extrasensory perception of another world of spirits. Here and elsewhere, Kant classes Schwāmerei as a form of madness.

Kant's Account of Theoretical Fanatism

Kant's association of theoretical fanatics with visionaries and mystical, such person claim directly to intuit events or entities that transcend ordinary sensible experience. Kant's was mistaking to such claim to knowledge, he denies that human beings are capable of any knowledge concerning the supersensible or things in themselves, of things not as they appear to (natural) sensibility. The fanatical claim to knowledge is thus mistaken, on Kant's view, because it confuses sensible and intelligible objects and/or corresponding type of knowledge. Hence, Kant's claim that human beings can attain knowledge of things in themselves or noumena; the fanatical error is to fail to recognize that such knowledge may be obtained only through pure reason, not through sense experience or intuition (if we are not to know about things in themselves, this knowledge would be pure rational knowledge).

“The delusion of being able to see something beyond all bound of sensibility that is to know the supersensible through some sort of intuition, Swedenborg's claims to experience ghosts and Neo-Platonists putative direct apprehension of non-sensible ideas both constitute claims to “see”, intuit, directly perceive-ideas or entities that are beyond the reach of ordinary natural sensibility.” (Schneewind, 1998) This conception also

informs Kant's claim that Locke "open the door" to fanaticism, when he claims to have a direct sensible experiential premises.

Kant's Account of Practical Fanaticism

Kant's practical fanaticism provides some obvious materials for criticism of fanaticism, those that involve immoral action, including action that harms the fanatical agent himself may be condemned as violations of the moral law. The claim that "God told me" to do such thing cannot, moreover justify the abrogation of the moral law. We say God is the Good if thus is the case will "God" tell you to harm yourself or someone else which is morally against the law? Is that act legitimate?

For, Kant's argues, that the only legitimate, practically rational conception of God is derived from morality itself. (E.g. as a "holy will" that acts in accord with the moral law infallibly, or as the guarantor of the possibility of the highest good). Thus, God cannot consistently be understood to command that which is immoral. More so, in so far as the fanatic invokes God's command as a guide to action as opposed to or simply independently of moral law, as the law of pure practical reason itself, the fanatic act heteronomously.

Locke does not explicitly discuss practical fanaticism, but he alludes to "action" or "conduct", indicating that practical fanaticism may be seen as either a type or a result of cognitive error of enthusiasm. According to Locke, practical fanaticism was seen as enthusiasm, relating to moral or practical belief: The enthusiast might believe that "one ought to kill all non-believers" as a practical truth, revealed to him by God, and therefore act upon this belief. The fanatic is someone who makes false claims to knowledge about the highest things or being (God), with the most absolute authority (as from God). Consequently, the fanatic will consider himself justified in acting to promote those beliefs by any means necessary, to the exclusion or violation of other interests and common moral beliefs, thinking that he/she is pleasing God. Thus, Locke suggests that the enthusiast "Tyrannizes over his own mind" (by believing something without evidence) and therefore will be inclined to impose upon others.

1. God cannot consistently be understood to command that which is immoral, as the fanatic invokes God's command as a guide to action as opposed to moral law.

-
2. “The concept of omni benevolence is logically contradictory because the fanatic claim that God told him/her through revelation to carry out an act which when considered is evil and not morally right or legitimate, (violation of moral law) ” it does not justify the goodness of God” (Sedgwick, 2008).
 3. Immanuel Kant posits in his criticism of Benedict Spinoza “causality” that every evil in the existential realm must be traced to a “cause”, God cannot be the cause of fanatical ideologies, which include torture, jingoism, hatred, threats, suppressions and even death. The benevolence of God cannot be contradicted, which becomes a paradox that does not follow logical sequence.
 4. The learner observed that his criticism (Immanuel Kant) on subsequent philosophers’ traditional argument where invalid, he classified them into three kinds, namely, the ontological argument, the cosmological argument and the physic-theological argument. My take is that his submission is subjective and not objective because his submission was lacking in logic for ontologically, God permit freewill embedded in moral choice and moral responsibly.

Logical Reasoning

A fanatic believes himself to feel an immediate and extraordinary communion with a higher nature; that is the case of religious fanaticism. Religious fanaticism appears to be the deadliest of all fanatical assumptions because of its claims of divine being. This is another form of authoritarianism, it is a jingoistic attitude that can be social, political or religious; the crux of such belief is embedded in human nature “religious fanaticism or religious extremism” is a pejorative designation used to indicate uncritical zeal or obsessive enthusiasm that is related to one’s own or one’s group’s devotion to a religion.” Historically, human nature has been led toward lots of irrational ideas and belief. The views as asserted within some observable historical period with: Judaism, Zoroastrianism, Christianity, Hinduism, and African Traditional Religion. The above-mentioned world religions have participated in one defined form this fanaticism. An illogical ideology that places its core belief and values above every other could be viewed as subjective illogical human reasoning. However, it must be noted that most religious fanatics pursue their goals rigidly with every element of curiosity. Fanatics are also believed to be

persons or group of individuals who can use unconventional means to assert their belief; such means include death, pains, torture, force, coercion, emotional blackmail, intimidation, starvation. Other means which violates social existing order which could be; moral, political or legal.

Psychological fanaticism is rooted in one's ontological defects, that is; fear, anxiety and phenomena of uncertainty. Psychological phenomena which are in themselves products of human illogical imagination can certainly lead to a lot of irrational thought which is geared towards displacing the imagery circumstances created by their imagining walls. "The social identity – defining devotion to a sacred value that demands universal recognition and complemented by a hostility towards dissent thereby takes the aforementioned form of hostile antagonism rightly correspond to human illogical pursuit of protective imaginary adventure leading to a culture of exclusion." This happens to be the case in northern Nigeria which is predominantly Muslim. The cult of fanatics has taken the bane of religion in northwestern Nigeria resulting to colossal destructions of lives and properties.

Why Logical Reasoning

Logical reasoning is a form of thinking in which premises and relations between premise are leased in a rigorous manner to infer conclusion that are entailed by the premises and relations. Logical reasoning thus promotes rational thoughts. It involves the use of data to ascertain and deduce facts. Rational reasoning involves the use of logic which will draw conclusions from related premises. It happens in form of interferences or arguments to a conclusion supported by the premises. Kant's argument on fanaticism lacks logical reasoning because accurate conclusion was not drawn based on identify premises. has the following importance:

Logical reasoning is important because:

1. Help to solve the problem of decision making
2. Help to provide solution to uncertainties
3. Help to discern the truth
4. Help to readjust mindset.
5. It helps in formations of set objectives

There are three kinds of logical reasoning:

- ✓ ***Deductive reasoning:*** This is a process of drawing valid inferences. An inference is valid if its conclusion follows logically from its premises; meaning that it is impossible for the premises to be true and

conclusion to be false. Deductive reasoning offers the strongest support; the premises ensure the conclusion (meaning it is impossible for the conclusion to be false if all premises are true).

- ✓ **Inductive reasoning:** This is a form of general ligation that infers a universal law from a pattern found in many individual cases. It can be used on many individual observations example of black ravens. This is a general assertion derived from body observations. The truth however, of inductive reasoning un-like deductive argument is at best probable based on the observable evidence.
- ✓ **Adductive reasoning:** This means the precondition is using the conclusion and the rule to assume that the precondition could explain the conclusion. Example: when it rains the grass get wet, the grass is wet, it must have rained. Diagnosticians and defectives are commonly associated with this style of reasoning. This is to fully differentiate from deductive and inductive reasoning seemly used by Immanuel Kant's which can produce unreliable sequence of ideas.

This research has examined the concept of God, atheism, the existence of the Supreme Being in relation to fanatical human tendency. Immanuel Kant argued that religion ought to be governed by republican government; that freedom of religion must be curtailed and "that morality must be derived from principles of pure practical reason. Human beings should legitimately know scientific law concerning objects of sensible experience but not to have knowledge of God or other spiritual, supersensible matters. The assertions' is that Immanuel Kant's ontological argument for the existence of God lacks logical merits and that religious beliefs necessitated fanaticism. His ontological argument lacks both deductive and inductive reasoning. It also lacks logical cohesion because there are other irreligious fanatic ideologies. His ontological argument on the existence of God lacks deductive and inductive reasoning.

Summary and Conclusion

The fanatic immerses himself in the ecstatic believe to be in union with God, to have immediate experience of God and thereby disassociating himself from reasoning. These tend to give an understanding of God as a separate being, to be pleased or flattered. This delusion arises, correspondingly, not because of the agent's experience of "heavenly feeling" but because of the wrong conception of God anthropomorphically, in accord with the analogy of

human moral error. This research has examined the concept of God, atheism, and the existence of Supreme Being in relation to fanatical human tendencies. Kant account of fanaticism is an absolute endorsement of an ideology (often religious), taken to justify violent and immoral action and argued that initial prove for the existence of God by numerous philosophers (Hobbes, Spinoza, Locke, Shaftesbury, Hume and Voltaire) does not provide credible "Faith Reason" he rather opined that religion must be governed by Reason and Knowledge of human nature alone; thus suggesting that legitimacy of morality must be inspired by scientific advances controlled by government and not knowledge of "Speculations" by overzealous theistic thinkers.

Recommendations

God, freedom, and immortality not as metaphysical certainties but as regulative ideas necessary for moral reasoning. Kant's warns against theoretical dogmatism; practical fanaticism similarly arises when these postulates are treated as objects of empirical or mystical certainty rather than practical commitments. This helps avoid mistaking moral faith for fanatical conviction. For Kant's these ideas are needed to make sense of moral striving not to enforce dogma.

Kant's idea of moral faith (a rational commitment to the postulates grounded in duty) and practical fanaticism, where individuals act on absolute moral claims without regards for human limitation, fallibility, or context. Scharmer as a source of irrational zealotry true moral action must stem from reason and autonomy, not emotional excess or blind certainty.

Kant's stress the primacy of moral law and autonomy as central safeguards against practical fanaticism. A fanatic sacrifice reason to an external cause. Practical fanaticism often arises when people believe they are justified in violating moral limits "for higher cause." Kant's ethics denies this: no end justifies violating the categorical imperative.

References

- Allison, H. E. (1990). *Theory of Freedom*. Cambridge University Press. pp. 145-160.
<https://archive.org/details/kanstheoryoffre0000alli>
- Auxier, R. E. (2023). Kant, moral imagination, and pathologies of reason". *Studia Philosophica Wratislaviensia*, 17(4), 5-27.
<https://doi.org/10.19195/18958001.17.4.1>

- Beiser, F. C. (1987). The Fate of Reason. *The Fate of Reason*, 225 - 250.
<https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674020696>
- Guyer, P. (1993). The possibility of the categorical imperative. In *Kant and the Experience of freedom: Essay on aesthetics and mortality* (333-361).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139172516>
- Kant, I. (1987). *Critique of Judgment*. (W. S. Pluhar, Trans.; M. J. Gregor, Foreword) Hackett Publishing Company (p. 132).
- Kant, I. (2006). *Anthropolgy from a pragmatic point of view* (R. B. Loudon, Trans. Ed.' M. Kuehn, Introduction). Cambridge University Press. pp. 162-170.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511809569>
- Kant, I. (1889). *Critique of Prctical Reason and other works on the theory of ethics*. (T. K. Abbott, Trans.) Longmans, Green, and Co. pp. 230-240.
<https://archive.org/details/cu31924029021612>
- Kant, I. (1963). *Lecture on Ethcis*. (L. Infield, Trans.). Harper & Row. pp. 210-220.
<https://www.amazon.com/Kant-Lectures-Ethics-Hackett-Classics/dp/0915144263>
- Kant, I. (1960). *Religion with the limits of reason alone* (F. M. Greene & H. H. Hudson Trans.). Harper & Row. pp. 200-210.
https://archive.org/details/religionwithinli0000kant_r6f5
- Korsgaard, C. M. (1996). *Creating the Kingdom Ends*. Cambridge University Press. pp. 112-130. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139174503>
- Palmquist, S. R. (1993). *Kant's system of perspective: An Architectonic interpretation of the critical philosophy*. University Press of America. pp. 145-160. <https://books.google.com/books?id=3kXXXXAAAMAAJ>
- Pasternack, L. R. (2014). *Routledge Philosophy guidebook to Kant on religion within the boundries of mere reason* Routledge. pp. 85-100.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315874302>
- Rohlf, M. (2024). *Immaneu Kant*. In E. N. Zalta (Ed), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2024 Edition). Standford University.
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/kant/>
- Schneewind, J. B. (1998). *The invention of autonomy: A history of modern moral philosophy*. Cambridge University Pres. pp. 562-570.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511818172>
- Sedgwick, S. S. (2008). *Kant's Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals: An introduction*. Cambridge University Press. pp. 168-199.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511809538>
- Wood, A. W. (1999). Kant's Ethical Thought. *Kant's Ethical Thought*. Cambridge University Press. pp. 145- 160.
https://archive.org/details/kantsethicalthou0000wood_u4m7
- Yovel, Y. (1980). *Kant and Philosophy History*. Princeton University Press. pp. 295-296.